

Translated survey questions, measured variable, and categorization of compensatory policies for:

Can compensatory policies make fossil fuel subsidy reform socially acceptable in Colombia?

Farah Mohammadzadeh Valencia, Charlotte Bez, Leonard Missbach, Jan Christoph Steckel, Brigitte Castañeda, Jorge Bonilla, Jorge Garcia

#	Question (translated from Spanish)	Variable
1	How old are you?	socio-dem
2	What is your gender?	socio-dem
3	According to your culture, ethnicity, or physical traits, do you identify as or are you recognized as:	socio-dem
4	What is the department where your main place of residence is located?	socio-dem
5	What is the municipality where your main place of residence is located?	socio-dem
6	How many people live in your household? Your household includes you, your family members living with you (including minors under 18 years old), and other dependent people living with you. Your household excludes apartment roommates.	socio-dem
7	What is the highest level of education you have attained?	socio-dem
8	What do you primarily do?	socio-dem
9	What was your household's MONTHLY income last month (including all sources of income, such as government support or family contributions)?	socio-dem
10	In which of the following groups would you place yourself based on your current income?	socio-dem
11	According to your home's electricity bill, what socioeconomic stratum do you belong to?	socio-dem
12	Do you or someone in your household have a motorcycle for household use?	VEHICLE USE
13	On average, how many days a week do you or someone in your household use the motorcycle(s)?	VEHICLE USE
14	Do you or someone in your household have a car for household use?	VEHICLE USE
15	On average, how many days a week do you or someone in your household use the car(s)?	VEHICLE USE
16	What type of fuel do you typically use in your car? Select all that apply:	VEHICLE USE (fuel type)
17	What is the approximate price of diesel/ACPM per liter in pesos (COP) right now near you?	Diesel price salience
18	Do you sometimes use public transportation?	VEHICLE USE public transport
19	On average, how many days a week do you use public transportation?	VEHICLE USE public transport
20	Do you sometimes use a taxi, Uber, DiDi, or another ride-hailing platform?	VEHICLE USE Taxi/Uber
21	On average, how many days a week do you use a taxi, Uber, DiDi, or another platform?	VEHICLE USE Taxi/Uber

22	Do you sometimes use a bicycle to get around?	VEHICKE USE Bike
23	On average, how many days a week do you use a bicycle to get around?	VEHICKE USE Bike
24	What type of energy or fuel do you MAINLY use at home for cooking?	COOKING
25	Please select "Strongly agree" to show that you are paying attention to this question.	Attention check
26	How informed do you consider yourself about climate change?	CLIMATE
27	How concerned are you about climate change?	CLIMATE
28	Which of the following statements do you most agree with? Climate change... 1. ... is an urgent problem that we need to deal with today 2. ... is not an urgent problem yet, but it will be in the future 3. ... is an urgent problem, but there is nothing to be done, it is too late to act 4. ... will never be a problem that needs to be dealt with 5. I am not sure	CLIMATE
29	Which of the following statements do you most agree with? 1. Priority must be given to the fight against climate change, regardless of its negative consequences for economic growth 2. Priority must be given to economic growth regardless of its negative consequences for the fight against climate change 3. Equal priority must be given to climate change and economic growth 4. I am not sure 5. Other:	CLIMATE
30	To what extent do you consider the following criteria important for the government to implement a policy to fight climate change? - A climate change policy should primarily reduce CO2 emissions - The financial costs of a climate policy should be low for me and my household - The financial costs of a climate policy should be distributed equitably among all households	CLIMATE
31	With which of the following political parties do you identify or have some affinity?	POLITICAL (support/non-supporter)
32	For which of the presidential candidates did you vote in the second round in 2022?	POLITICAL (support/non-supporter)
33	According to what the terms "left" and "right" mean to you, where would you place yourself on the political spectrum?	POLITICAL
34	Have you heard of any of the following proposals made by the elected president, Gustavo Petro? Select all that apply:	POLITICAL
35	Of the proposals you have heard from President Gustavo Petro, which do you understand? Select all that apply:	POLITICAL
36	Of the proposals you understand, which do you agree with? Select all that apply:	POLITICAL

37	<p>Would you say this country is...?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ...progressing 2. ...stagnating 3. ...regressing 4. I'd rather not say 	POLITICAL
38	<p>Please indicate for each of the following groups, institutions or people on the list how much confidence you have in them:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Armed Forces 2. The Police 3. The President of the Republic 4. The Governors 5. The Mayors 6. The Political Parties 7. The Congress of the Republic 8. The Constitutional Court 9. The Supreme Court of Justice 	Trust in govt
39	How would you rate the functioning of democracy in Colombia?	democracy
40	How would you generally rate the current economic situation in the country?	State of economy
41	Please indicate through which of the following media options you inform yourself about the country's political news. Select all that apply.	NEWS
42	Do you believe that the price of fuel is subsidized in Colombia?	SUBSIDY KNOWLEDGE
43	Do you believe that diesel/ACPM prices are currently subsidized in Colombia?	SUBSIDY KNOWLEDGE
44	Do you believe that gasoline prices are currently subsidized in Colombia?	SUBSIDY KNOWLEDGE
45	Do you believe that if gasoline prices were to increase, food prices in supermarkets would be affected?	SUBSIDY KNOWLEDGE
46	Do you believe that if diesel/ACPM prices were to increase, food prices in supermarkets would be affected?	SUBSIDY KNOWLEDGE
47	How much do you consider yourself to have benefited from fuel subsidies over the last 12 months?	SUBSIDY KNOWLEDGE
48	To what extent do you believe your household is entitled to benefit from fuel subsidies?	FAIRNESS TO ME
49	How much do you think a 65% increase in fuel prices would affect you?	FAIRNESS TO ME
50	How concerned are you about the effects on low-income people from a possible 65% increase in fuel prices?	FAIRNESS TO OTHERS
51	How concerned are you about the effects on high-income people from a possible 65% increase in fuel prices?	FAIRNESS TO OTHERS
52	Have there been protests in your municipality in recent weeks against the increase in diesel/ACPM prices?	PROTEST SALIENCE
53	If yes, Who or who have been leading the protests?	PROTEST SALIENCE
54	Attention check	Attention check

55 A	If fuel subsidies (gasoline and diesel/ACPM) were partially eliminated and prices increased by 65%, how much would your household expenses increase per month?	MICRO-SIM
55 B	Without changing their lifestyle, high-income households will have to spend more than low-income households if fuel prices such as gasoline and diesel/ACPM were to increase by 65%.	FAIRNESS TO OTHERS
55 C	In 2023, government spending on fuel subsidies was greater than its investments in road infrastructure in Colombia.	EFFICIENCY
55 D	Subsidies on fuels such as gasoline and diesel/ACPM contribute to climate change and promote environmental damage in Colombia such as extreme temperatures, droughts, forest fires, floods, and landslides.	ENV/CLIMATE CH
56	The government of Colombia should MAINTAIN fuel subsidies (gasoline and diesel/ACPM).	STATUS QUO
57	The government of Colombia should PARTIALLY REDUCE fuel subsidies (gasoline and diesel/ACPM), even though reducing the subsidies would raise the prices of these by 65%.	UNCONDITIONAL - PARTIAL
58	The government of Colombia should COMPLETELY ELIMINATE fuel subsidies (gasoline and diesel/ACPM), even though this would double the prices of fuels.	UNCONDITIONAL - COMPLETE
59	To what extent would you support the policy of partially reducing subsidies if the government of Colombia used the funds previously spent on fuel subsidies (gasoline and diesel/ACPM) to finance the following:	CONDITIONAL
59.1	Equal cash transfers to all households	Category (i): Uniform cash transfers Category (ii): social protection
59.2	Cash transfers to poor households	Category (i): Targeted cash transfers Category (ii): social protection
59.3	Cash transfers to households most affected by rising prices	Category (i): Targeted cash transfers Category (ii): social protection
59.4	Reduce personal income tax	Category (i): Tax reduction Category (ii): social protection
59.5	Reduce Colombia's public debt	Category (i): Public finance Category (ii) public goods
59.6	Investments in electric transport such as electric buses or cars	Category (i): Green spending Category (ii) public goods
59.7	Improve rural roads and paths in the countryside	Category (i): Green spending Category (ii) public goods
59.8	Improve education and public schools	Category (i): Other Category (ii) public goods

59.9	Investments in clean energy such as solar or wind energy	Category (i): Green spending Category (ii) public goods
59.10	Protect the Amazon rainforest and reduce deforestation	Category (i): Green spending Category (ii) public goods
60	Is there anything else you believe the government of Colombia could invest the funds from increased fuel prices in that would motivate you to support the government's decision to reduce fuel subsidies (gasoline and diesel/ACPM)?	
61	If 60 YES then open-ended question	
62	Do you consider that this survey asked politically biased questions?	BIAS